

Adsorption of Isolan (1-isopropyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolyl dimethyl carbamate) by Some Clay Minerals

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Studies in the adsorption of isolan on seven different types of sodium saturated clay minerals i.e. pyrophyllite, hectorial hector, fuller's earth, kaolinite illite, bentonite (Na) and montmorillonite were carried out at 15 and 25°. The adsorption isotherms of isolan on clay minerals are of S-shape and it is seen that adsorption increases with the increase of concentration. The order of adsorption is found to be montmorillonite > bentonite(Na) > illite > kaolinite > fuller's earth > hectorial hector > pyrophyllite. This is attributed to higher adsorption capacity of montmorillonite. Adsorption of isolan decreases with the increase in temperature indicating the involvement of van der Waals forces during adsorption process. The equilibrium was established in less than 24 hours of the exposure time. The data obtained satisfy the Freundlich equation. The value of K was higher in the case of bentonite(Na) and montmorillonite which indicated stronger binding of the insecticide with the clay minerals. Also the value of $\Delta\bar{G}$ (partial molar free energy) was found to be maximum in the case of montmorillonite.

The results for the apparent heats of adsorption reveal that the adsorption of isolan is physical in nature. Desorption of isolan with aqueous solution of surfactant was minimum in the case of montmorillonite showing stronger binding of isolan with it and also because of the expanding nature of the clay mineral-

THE clay mineral is the colloidal fraction of the soil which is responsible for adsorption due to its high surface area and high density of the surface charge. The phenomenon of adsorption is of great importance to understand the fate and metabolism of pesticides applied to soils.

Adsorption of pesticides has been investigated by a number of workers including Bailey and White¹ who reviewed the literature pertaining to (i) adsorption and desorption of organic pesticides by soil colloids, (ii) movement of pesticides through soils and soil surface and (iii) physico-chemical properties of soil constituents which influence pesticide adsorption and desorption. Weber² discussed the mechanism of adsorption of s-triazine by clay colloids and observed that the herbicides are readily adsorbed by a variety of soil clay minerals including montmorillonite, illite and kaolinite. Chopra and Goel³ studied the adsorption of lindane on three different types of soils and reported that the adsorption increased with the increase in concentration and obeyed Freundlich equation. Van Bladel⁴ observed that the adsorption of fenuron(I) on montmorillonite was decreased by increasing temperature and increased with the lowering of p^H .

The present studies were taken with a view to understand surface behaviour of different clays towards adsorption and desorption of isolan.

Experimental

Preparation of the clays :

The reference clays for this work were obtained from Wards Natural Science Establishment, New York (U.S.A.) and are designated as follows :

Montmorillonite (Bentonite), Upton, Wyoming.
Pyrophyllite, Robbins, North Carolina.
Illite, Morris Illinois.
Kaolinite, Bath, South Carolina.
Bentonite (Na), Upton, Wyoming.
Hectorial Hector-34 (Hector-California).
Fuller's Earth, India.

The minerals were ground and then passed through 200 mesh sieve. Each clay mineral was saturated with 1N NaCl and then washed with alcohol to remove chloride. The samples were dried and then passed through 200 mesh sieve and stored in sealed glass container for use.

Adsorption Experiments :

One hundred mg of each of the sodium saturated clay mineral was weighed into glass stoppered reagent bottles. A stock solution of isolan in chloroform (500 μg per ml) was prepared. Suitable aliquots of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10 ml were added to different bottles. The final suspension was made to 10 ml by adding chloroform in each case. The adsorption was carried out for 24 hours and the

samples were incubated at 25°. Similar adsorption experiments were performed by incubating the samples at 15 and 25° for 0, 2, 4, 6, 8, 16, 24, 48 hours respectively taking the concentration of isolan 5000 µg in each case. The samples were then centrifuged and the pesticide was determined.

Analysis of Isolan :

Isolan in solution was determined by colorimetric method of Dowden⁵. Isolan was hydrolyzed in an alkaline solution to give dimethylamine which was distilled off and condensed in 0.1 N HCl. The dimethylamine was determined by reacting it with carbon disulfide and cupric ion to form yellow-brown copper dimethyl-dithiocarbamate. The optical density was measured at 436 nm using Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20.

Desorption Experiment :

The mineral weighing 100 mg each was taken in separate reagent bottles. Isolan weighing 5000 µg in chloroform was added and total volume was made to 20 ml with chloroform. The contents were equilibrated for 24 hours at 25°. The solution was separated by centrifugation. Fifty ml of extracting solution of 2% sodium lauryl sulphate was added to the residual material. The contents were shaken at 50 strokes per minute in an electric shaker for 4 hours. The samples were then centrifuged and isolan in the extract was determined as described earlier.

Results and Discussion

The amounts of isolan adsorbed per 100 mg of the mineral at 15 and 25°, were plotted against the equilibrium concentration to know the quantity adsorbed with the change in concentration and temperature. The adsorption isotherms are shown in figures 1 and 2. The isotherms are of S-shape according to the classification given by Giles and MacEwan⁶. The initial direction of curvature of S-shape isotherms show that there was a higher increase in adsorption with the increase in concentration of isolan. The S-shaped curve usually appears when three conditions are fulfilled regarding the solute molecules (a) it is monofunctional, that is, the solute molecule has a fairly large hydrophobic residue (>C₈) and a marked localisation of the forces of attraction for the substrate over a short section of its periphery and that it is adsorbed as a single unit and not in the form of a micell, (b) it has moderate intermolecular attraction, causing it to pack vertically in regular array in the adsorbed

Fig. 1 Adsorption isotherms for isolan on clay minerals at two different temperatures 15 and 25°C

Fig. 2 Adsorption isotherms for isolan on clay minerals at two different temperature 15 and 25°C

layer and (c) it meets strong competition, for substrate sites, from molecules of solvent or from another species.

The order of adsorption is montmorillonite > bentonite(Na) > illite > kaolinite > fuller's earth > hectorial hector > pyrophyllite. It has been found that adsorption of isolan by montmorillonite is about 1.5 times as compared to pyrophyllite, 1.4 times that of hectorial hector, 1.13 times that of fuller's earth, 1.1 times more as compared to kaolinite, 1.06 times greater than illite and 1.04 times greater than bentonite(Na).

The adsorption capacities of different clay minerals are different as is clear from the order of adsorption mentioned above. In order to explain this we should consider different characteristics, viz. structure of clay, charge density and surface area, etc., which are responsible for the difference in adsorption capacity.

As regards, the structure of the clay minerals, the basic layer of montmorillonite, illite and pyrophyllite, hectorial hector is 2 : 1 type because it is a combination of two tetrahedrally coordinated sheets of silica one on either side of an octahedrally coordinated sheet of alumina. The thickness of a single 2 : 1 layer is about 9.5 Å. All the tips of the tetrahedrons in case of montmorillonite are in the same direction and point towards the centre of the unit. The tetrahedral and octahedral sheets are combined in such a way that the tips of the tetrahedrons of each silicate sheet and one of the hydroxyl layers of the octahedral sheet form a common layer. The crystal lattice of montmorillonite expands very readily because the structural units are loosely held by weak oxygen-oxygen linkages⁷.

The structure of pyrophyllite is similar to that of montmorillonite except for the expanding lattice characteristics as the former does not show expansion.

The unit of illite is the same as that for the montmorillonite except that some of the silicon atoms are replaced by aluminium and the resultant charge deficiency is balanced by potassium ions. These ions occur between unit layers where they just fit into perforations in the surface layers. There is slight expansion in the crystal lattice of illite.

The crystal lattice of hectorial hector is also of the 2 : 1 type. It has magnesium and no aluminium.

Kaolinite is a 1 : 1 type mineral composed of one sheet of tetrahedrally coordinated cations with one sheet of octahedrally coordinated cations and the lattice is totally non-expanding.

The surface areas of some of clays calculated by the BET method using water vapour as the sorbate are 558.6, 239.4, 146.3 and 78.6 m²/g for montmorillonite, pyrophyllite, illite and kaolinite, respectively. Kaolinite has less sorption capacity as it has low surface area (78.6 m²/g) and low charge density and

the organic compounds are adsorbed on edges or faces of the clay particles, rather than in the interior of the lattice.

From the data we have seen that montmorillonite exhibited maximum adsorption of isolan. This can be attributed to the high charge density and high surface area of montmorillonite as discussed above. Adsorption on montmorillonite occurred not only on the external surface but also on the interiors of the lattice. Frissel⁸ also showed that the adsorption of various herbicides, by montmorillonite, was greater than that by illite or kaolinite. Similar observations have also been reported by Weber *et al*⁹ on the adsorption of diquat and paraquat by clay minerals and exchange resins.

Effect of Temperature and Exposure Time :

It is seen that the amount of isolan adsorbed on all the clay minerals decreases with the rise of temperature (Figs. 1 & 2). This is a general observation in adsorption process which is exothermic. With the rise in temperature, the kinetic energy of the molecules already bound and those of the approaching ones, increases and hence the electrostatic attraction decreases which ultimately results in a decrease in adsorption. The decrease is marked in all the cases. Higher temperature may cause a disruption of hydrogen bonds if this were the primary bonding mechanism. These results are further corroborated by the observations on the adsorption results of prometone on montmorillonite made by Weber *et al*⁹.

The effect of temperature on adsorption equilibrium is direct indication of the energy of adsorption and the weaker interactions show the adverse effect of temperature which may indirectly influence the solubility of the organic compound. In general, both these factors work together and lead to less adsorption at higher temperature. Bartell *et al*¹⁰ found that at higher concentration of butyl alcohol the temperature effects on solubility were more important than the effects on adsorption.

The temperature effects become more complex where there is no change in the amount adsorbed with the rise of temperature. Harris and Warren¹¹ showed that the adsorption of simazine, atrazine and 2, 4-D on muck soil is not temperature dependent which shows the presence of exchange reactions which are not temperature dependent.

Adsorption by all clay minerals at different time intervals and at 15 and 25° is also dependent on temperature. At low temperature the adsorption is more in all the cases under investigation.

From a perusal of the data plotted in Figures 3 & 4, it is clear that major portion of isolan was adsorbed by all minerals in less than 24 hours of contact. The additional amount of the compound

Fig. 3. Effect of Temperature and Time on Adsorption of Isolan on Clay Minerals

Fig. 4. Effect of Temperature and Time on Adsorption of Isolan on Clay Minerals.

adsorbed on the clay minerals occurred between 24 to 48 hours at both the temperatures. In all cases higher amount is adsorbed at low temperature in the same time interval.

Freundlich Adsorption Equation :

The data of the Table 1 obey empirical isothermal Freundlich relationship :

$$\frac{X}{m} = KC^n$$

A plot of $\log \frac{X}{m}$ versus $\log C$ resulted in a series of straight lines for different clay minerals. Extrapolation of the plots to $\log C = 0$ gave $\log K$ which was the amount of isolan adsorbed on the clay mineral.

The slope of the lines could be calculated $\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)$ from the data. The plots are shown in Figures 5 and 6. The values of empirical constants K and n are given below :

	Pyrophy- illite	Hectorial hactor	Fuller's earth	Kaoli- nite	Illite	Bento- nite (Na)	Montmori- llonite
K	0.023	0.029	0.132	0.200	0.457	1.202	1.148
n	0.484	0.500	0.600	0.684	0.788	1.000	1.000

The value of constant n is indicative of the degree of non-linearity between solution concentration and adsorption and its value greater than unity indicates that relative adsorption decreases with increasing concentration. The constant K is a measure of the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION ON ADSORPTION OF ISOLAN ON CLAY MINERALS AT 25°* (µg)

Initial conc. of Isolan (µg)	Pyrophyllite	Hectorial hector	Fuller's earth	Kaolinite	Illite	Bentonite	Montmori-llonite
500	100	100	100	125	175	300	400
1000	150	175	200	212	425	450	500
1500	500	500	525	550	600	800	850
2000	550	600	650	650	1000	1050	1100
2500	900	950	950	1075	1250	1400	1550
3000	1000	1075	1200	1550	1550	1600	1700
4000	1200	1425	1600	2000	1950	2050	2525
5000	2150	2275	2325	2400	2550	2700	2900

* The amounts of Isolan adsorbed are in micrograms.

Fig. 5. The Freundlich Adsorption Isotherms of Isolan on Clay Minerals at 25°C

Fig. 6. The Freundlich Adsorption Isotherms of Isolan on Clay Minerals at 25°C

strength of adsorption. Hence the binding of isolan is stronger in case of bentonite(Na) and montmorillonite.

The slopes of the plots of adsorption of isolan on the clay minerals are different. Yuen and Hilton¹² showed that the K values alone are insufficient to characterise adsorption behaviour of a compound on a group of clay minerals; the K value and slope of the line for a given chemical would, however, be sufficient to give a characteristic plot for most of the recommended doses of concentration.

Evaluation of Free-Energy Change :

As a result of adsorption, the change in partial molar free energy of the system $\Delta \bar{G}$ can be calculated from the thermodynamic relationship :

$$\Delta \bar{G} = -RT \ln \frac{C_S}{C_0}$$

where C_S is the equilibrium concentration and C_0 is the initial concentration of the solution before adsorption. The change in this thermodynamic function that occurs when a chemical is adsorbed can be used to measure the driving force of a reaction. From a perusal of the results (Table 2), it

TABLE 2—AVERAGED $\Delta \bar{G}$ (PARTIAL MOLAR FREE ENERGY) VALUES FOR ISOLAN ADSORBED BY CLAY MINERALS AT 25°

Adsorbent	Isolan $\Delta \bar{G}$ (cal/mole)
Pyrophyllite	-245.057
Hectorial hector	-234.471
Fuller's earth	-251.286
Kaolinite	-298.966
Illite	-354.677
Bentonite (Na)	-454.468
Montmorillonite	-565.098

becomes clear that in the case of isolan the average value of $\Delta \bar{G}$ is the highest for montmorillonite and the least for hectorial hector showing that the driving force is more for montmorillonite as compared to that of other clay minerals.

Apparent Heats of Adsorption :

The apparent heats of adsorption were calculated from the isotherms using Clausius Clapeyron equation¹³. It is found that, greater the difference in adsorption at two temperatures with the same equilibrium concentration, the higher is the heat of adsorption (Table 3).

TABLE 3—APPARENT HEATS OF ADSORPTION OF ISOLAN ON CLAY MINERALS

Adsorbent	Temperature range (°C)	Equilibrium concentration (μ g)	ΔH (-K cal/mole)
Pyrophyllite	15-25	1600-2000	6.4-4.5
Hectorial hector	15-25	1600-2000	5.4-3.0
Fuller's earth	15-25	1600-2000	4.4-3.9
Kaolinite	15-25	1600-2000	7.2-5.2
Illite	15-25	1600-2000	4.1-3.5
Bentonite (Na)	15-25	1600-2000	1.8-1.4
Montmorillonite	15-25	1600-2000	1.6-0.6

The magnitude of apparent heats of adsorption is not a direct indication of the number of bonds formed between adsorbent and adsorbate, but the algebraic sum of the heat changes taking place in the two successive processes (a) the removal of adsorbate from association with the solvent and (b) the attachment of the adsorbate to the adsorbent.

The values of the heats of adsorption of isolan

indicate that adsorption is physical in nature as heats of adsorption fall within a range of 1-10 K cal/mole. Also there is first the formation of monolayer on the surface followed by a build up of multilayers.

Desorption of Isolan :

The amount of isolan adsorbed by the clay minerals has been extracted using solution of sodium lauryl sulphate. The amounts of isolan displaced from the clay minerals are given in Table 4. It is

TABLE 4—PERCENTAGE OF ISOLAN DESORBED BY SODIUM LAURYL SULPHATE (SURFACTANT)

Montmorillonite	2.59
Bentonite (Na)	5.55
Illite	5.86
Hectorial hector	9.89
Pyrophyllite	11.63
Fuller's earth	35.16
Kaolinite	50.50

seen that only about 2.59% of adsorbed compound is released from montmorillonite. Maximum amount viz. 50.5% of adsorbed isolan is desorbed from kaolinite. This is in accordance with the work of Weber *et al*⁹, who observed desorption of 5% diquat and paraquat adsorbed on montmorillonite and 80% of these adsorbed cations on kaolinite by treatment with 1M BaCl₂ solution. This indicates that isolan adsorbed on the edges of kaolinite clay particles are not held as strongly as those bound within the clay lattice of the montmorillonite. Possibly coulombic forces are responsible for adsorption on kaolinite, whereas in the case of montmorillonite system some of the pesticide is adsorbed on the inside of the layers which becomes difficult to extract. This is an important distinction between the two clays. In the other clays the amount released ranges from 5.55 to 35.16 per cent.

Conclusions :

From the above discussion it is indicated that isolan is adsorbed very strongly on montmorillonite and least on pyrophyllite and the sequence of adsorption follows the trends of surface area and charge density which is, of course highest for montmorillonite.

It is further confirmed that values of apparent heats of adsorption is lowest in montmorillonite which show the ease with which isolan is adsorbed. The value of n which is slope of isotherm is maximum in case of montmorillonite and bentonite-(Na) has further supported that isolan is strongly adsorbed on these two minerals. These are further supported by $\Delta\bar{G}$ values. Description results also indicate that isolan is strongly bound on montmorillonite.

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